

Deliverable D20.1

Second Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows

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Abbreviations

AAAI – Accountability, Authentication, Authorisation & Identity (ENTRUST WP18)
AAI – Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API – Application Programming Interface
BSC – Barcelona Supercomputing Center
COVID – Coronavirus Disease
DARE – Data & Analytics Research Environments (DARE UK programme)
EADD – ENTRUST Accountability/Audit Design Document
EGA – European Genome-Phenome Archive
ELIXIR – European Life-Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
EOSC – European Open Science Cloud
FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FUNNEL – Lightweight GA4GH TES Executor (“Funnel”)
GA4GH – Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GATK – Genome Analysis Toolkit
GUI – Graphical User Interface
HDR UK – Health Data Research UK
HPC – High-Performance Computing
JSON – JavaScript Object Notation
LTS – Long-Term Support (software maintenance)
MinIO – S3-compatible Object Storage System
OMOP – Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
OIDC – OpenID Connect
PII – Personally Identifiable Information
RO-Crate – Research Object Crate
S3 – Simple Storage Service (object storage interface)
SAREK – nf-core/Sarek workflow for germline/somatic genomics
SHACL – Shapes Constraint Language
SLURM – Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management
TES – Task Execution Service (GA4GH)
TESK – A Kubernetes-native TES executor
TRE – Trusted Research Environment
TRE-FX – Trusted Research Environment Federated Execution (DARE UK)
UI – User Interface
UNIMAN – University of Manchester
UNOTT – University of Nottingham
VM – Virtual Machine
WRROC – Workflow Run RO-Crate

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable (D20.1) presents the Second Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows (hereafter, the Demonstrator) developed under WP20 - Workflow Processing. It builds on Year 1 outputs D19.1¹, which provided the initial demonstrator and architectural approach for using RO-Crates and workflow technologies in TREs. In Year 2, the Demonstrator has matured into a fully deployable, federated prototype and demonstrated its capacity to run a cross-TRE “data pooling” federated analysis between TRE-FX (UNOTT) and TRE-BSC.

The Year 2 focus has been on improving deployment realism while enabling Five Safes-compliant executions, strengthening provenance, and enhancing federated interoperability. Development efforts centred around:

1. Adopting Five Safe TES principles, enabling policy-aware task execution across TREs using a common GA4GH TES interface.
2. Deployment of the Demonstrator in two ENTRUST TREs, aligning execution semantics across sites.
3. A production-ready RO-Crate Validation Service, supporting SHACL-based validation.
4. Enhancements to WfExS and Five Safe TES tooling for secure secrets handling within TREs
5. Validation of the Demonstrator in Driver use cases

Through these improvements, WP20 now provides a demonstrator capable of federated, provenance-rich, policy-aware execution, consistent with the Five Safes principles and usable by TREs with heterogeneous compute backends. The demonstrator provides a technical foundation for further alignment with WP18 (AAAI) on accountability capture, and integrates with ongoing UK efforts such as DARE UK TREvolution².

¹ EOSC-ENTRUST Deliverable 19.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14412862>

² TREVOLUTION: <https://dareuk.org.uk/trevolution/>

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18, WP19/20/21)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ³ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15, WP19/20/21)	Yes
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No

³ Elizabeth Green et al. The present and future of the Five Safes framework. Nov. 2023, doi: 10.29012/jpc.831

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (EOSC-ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No

3. Methods

3.1. Five Safes TES Weave

The Demonstrator integrates the Five Safes TES⁴ tooling developed as part of the UK HDR Federated Analytics Programme⁵ and DARE UK TRevolution initiative. The shared vision is to provide TREs with a consistent, policy-aware execution interface designed specifically for restricted analytics environments in combination with the standardisation of the execution layer, built on the GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES)⁶. The Five Safes TES implementation applied in EOSC-ENTRUST introduces:

- An air-gap compliant submission service exposing a TES API
- TES messages, incorporating Five Safes metadata and federation details – such as target Project, and TREs to federate to – using standard TES tags.
- TES compliant containerised execution backend in secure environments

This approach uses the GA4GH TES standard as a stable, cross-platform approach to computational work distribution, while embedding Five Safes principles at the architectural and governance level. This combination provides interoperability, security, and TRE governance retention.

As described in ‘D19.1’ and inherited from TRE-FX⁷ design, the Demonstrator adopts a layered architectural strategy in which the outer layer of the federated TREs (the TRE Controller Layer) enables interoperability with a central Submission Layer, while TRE inner layers (the Execution Layers) are maintained mainly unaltered. Adopting GA4GH TES in the current Demonstrator at the ‘Execution Layer’ level further underpins system adaptability, permitting the transparent compatibility of any TES implementation (e.g. TESK⁸, FUNNEL⁹) while supporting a unified, Five-Safe-aware workflow submission model. The approach greatly lowers the adoption barrier by TRE providers, as infrastructures require neither full homogenization of internal compute systems nor a local data governance model.

3.1.1. Multiple Backend Executors

The core component of the Execution Layer is the actual Executor that will process the task or workflow at the compute backend of the TRE. Taking profit that Five Safe TES is

⁴ Five Safe TES Weave: https://docs.federated-analytics.ac.uk/five_safes_tes

⁵ HDR Federated Analytics Programme:

<https://www.hdr.ac.uk/research/research-data-infrastructure/federated-analytics/>

⁶ GA4GH TES: <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/task-execution-service-tes/>

⁷ TRE-FX: <https://trefx.uk/>

⁸ TESK: <https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/TESK>

⁹ FUNNEL: <https://github.com/ohsu-comp-bio/funnel>

executor-agnostic, as long as it provides a TES interface, we meant to employ two Executors within the Demonstrator addressing different analysis models:

- *FUNNEL*: a minimal TES executor that runs a single TES task exactly “as-is,” without additional orchestration layers, running one container per executor defined in the task, over a common shared filesystem volume. Per TES, executors are run sequentially and can therefore be used for straightforward serial workflows. Its lightweight design makes it well suited for simple or diagnostic computations, rapid prototyping, and federated queries that do not require workflow semantics, complex staging, or RO-Crate provenance generation.
- *WfExS-backend*¹⁰: a full workflow execution backend capable of running multi-step, provenance-rich workflows within restricted computing environments. WfExS provides encrypted staging, secrets handling, dataset-propagation controls, and complete WRROC (Workflow-run RO-Crate) provenance generation, making it the preferred choice for robust, governed execution of complex pipelines. However, it is not offering a TES standard interface, and ongoing work is addressing this point, as described in the section [WfExS as TES Backend](#).

Depending on the complexity and provenance needs of a given analytical scenario, either a lightweight container executor or a full workflow orchestrator may be selected. This choice is showcased well across the different ENTRUST Drivers for which the Demonstrator is acting as early prototype - as discussed in section [Collaborations and Drivers alignment](#).

3.2. RO-crates as integration methodology

3.2.1. Background

Research Object Crate (RO-Crate¹¹) is a community-developed method for FAIR packaging of research data with structured metadata, building on established Web standards¹², used in a multitude of domains¹³. The base RO-Crate specification can be extended with “profiles” to support the metadata needs of different domains and types of data. A few of these are relevant to EOSC-ENTRUST:

- Workflow RO-Crate¹⁴ for describing workflows, supported by WorkflowHub¹⁵.

¹⁰ WfExS: <https://github.com/inab/WfExS-backend>

¹¹ RO-Crate, <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

¹² Stian Soiland-Reyes, et al. Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate. *Data Science* 5(2):97-138 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>

¹³ RO-Crate in use, https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/use_cases

¹⁴ Workflow RO-Crate, <https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/>

¹⁵ Ove Johan Ragnar Gustafsson, et al. WorkflowHub: a registry for computational workflows. *Sci Data* 12, 837 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04786-3>

- The Workflow Run RO-Crate (WRROC)¹⁶ profile collection for capturing the provenance of executions of computational processes or workflows. The different profiles offer different levels of granularity¹⁷; the Workflow Run Crate profile in particular is supported by WfExS workflow engine orchestrator, as well as Galaxy and Nextflow workflow engines.
- Five Safes RO-Crate¹⁸ for describing workflow execution in TREs, including the provenance of Five Safes processes like workflow approval and disclosure control. This profile is currently being adopted in TRE infrastructures through the EOSC-ENTRUST, HDR UK, DARE UK, and ELIXIR Fed-A-Crate programs.

These profiles build on each other, so that a Workflow Run Crate exported from a workflow engine such as WfExS can be enriched with further metadata from other TRE services (services such as the different layers in Five Safes TES) to align with the Five Safes RO-Crate profile.

Following the Five Safes RO-Crate profile allows TRE processes to be made transparent without revealing sensitive data, as data can be referenced in an RO-Crate without being included directly. Five Safes RO-Crate also facilitates metadata exchange between different components of a TRE architecture by providing a shared, open standard which each component can map to.

3.2.2. Strategy

To support adoption and interoperability, it is important to ensure that generated crates align with the profile specifications. This enhances trust by ensuring that valid RO-Crates are complete and well-described; strengthens reproducibility by promoting consistent structuring; reduces the need for manual review and supports governance processes; and improves interoperability by ensuring that crates produced in one TRE (e.g., TRE A) can be reliably interpreted in another (e.g., TRE B).

The rocrate-validator package¹⁹ is an existing tool that offers thorough validation against the base RO-Crate specification and numerous profiles, including Workflow RO-Crate and the Workflow Run RO-Crate profile collection. The package can also be extended to support validation against additional profiles; this is needed to fully support the Five Safes RO-Crate profile.

To perform validation operations within TRE infrastructures, a service which provides an API wrapper for the rocrate-validator tool is needed. The service should be able to receive

¹⁶ Workflow Run RO-Crate, <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/profiles/>

¹⁷ Simone Leo, et al. Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate. PLoS ONE 19(9): e0309210 (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0309210>

¹⁸ Stian Soiland-Reyes, et al. TRE-FX Technical Documentation - Five Safes RO-crate. Zenodo (2023)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376350>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/crs4/rocrate-validator>

crates and return validation results, ideally without requiring external network access; this latter requirement facilitates use within a TRE if desired. In this demonstrator, the service will sit in between the submission layer and the TRE layer (see [Figure 1](#)), in order to validate RO-Crates at the submission and post-egress stages. The service will take the form of a deployable microservice, known as the RO-Crate Validation Service²⁰, that is being developed by UNIMAN.

²⁰ <https://github.com/eScienceLab/Cratey-Validator>

Fig. 1 - Sequence diagram²¹ illustrating submission and egress flow with RO-Crate Validation Service at submission and post-egress stages.

²¹ Sequence Diagram: [Sequence Diagram Vector Source](#); [Crate Validation Service Diagram Source](#)

3.3. Collaborations and Drivers alignment

As described in ‘D19.1’, the Demonstrator’s methodological approach has been developed in close alignment with EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint v1²², ensuring architectural consistency and maximising interoperability, while maximizing alignment with the updated version of the functional requirements²³ derived from EOSC-ENTRUST driver projects. The alignment effort is made obvious particularly for Driver 1 and Driver 3, that have taken the current Demonstrator as their real-world validator for federated workflow processing technology:

- Driver 1: Cross-national variant calling over aligned reads hosted in two TREs
- Driver 3: Cross-national federated analysis of RCT and RWD across two TREs to compare comorbidities in older adults vaccinated against COVID-19

The main commonality between Drivers 1 and 3 is that they both require “isolated” analytical federation type²⁴, well supported by the Demonstrator, where data is analysed in each TRE and aggregated results are pooled in one of the TRE within the federation. On the other hand, the analytical requirements on the backend constitute the bigger difference between Drivers; while Driver 3 aims for a lightweight statistical analysis federated query, Driver 1 aims to run a high-demand genomic pipeline with more complex run provenance requirements. Exploiting the Demonstrator’s capability of integrating any TES compliant execution backend, the Driver 3 prototype includes Funnel, while the Driver 1 prototype uses WfExS.

On the other hand, the Demonstrator is being designed with an extensible and sustainable logger system that will permit it to become the technical implementation of WP AAAI. The collaboration goal is to evaluate the feasibility of capturing, validating, and exporting the accountability-relevant events defined in the Accounting/Auditing Design Document (EADD-001)²⁵ (e.g. identity verification, authorisation decisions) as described in section [Next steps](#).

Beyond EOSC-ENTRUST, the Demonstrator technology and its approach is fully aligned with the TREvolution²⁶ project, part of the DARE UK program developing and adopting both, Five Safe TES tools to enable a UK federated scenario, and the use of RO-Crates for provenance metadata packing.

²² EOSC ENTRUST Blueprint year 1: <https://zenodo.org/records/14362388>

²³ EOSC ENTRUST MS8: [Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers](#)

²⁴ FedA analytical patterns:

https://docs.federated-analytics.ac.uk/federated_research_patterns/patterns

²⁵ Accounting/Auditing Design Document (EADD-001):

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/184u-2R4nduZwEB6g7AQziWWuSpA8ODw2/edit>

²⁶ TREvolution, <https://dareuk.org.uk/trevolution/>

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1. Expand and validate Five Safes RO-Crate interoperability use

4.1.1. RO-Crate Validation Service

The main development phase of the RO-Crate Validation Service²⁷ was completed in August 2025. The service provides automated checks to assess whether an RO-Crate conforms to the rules of its declared profile, identify missing or inconsistent information, and explain any issues detected.

The service is implemented as a Flask-based API²⁸ which uses the rocrate-validator²⁹ package to perform RO-Crate validation, avoiding duplication of existing tooling. The API exposes endpoints to request validation of RO-Crates stored in an object store, retrieve validation results, and validate submitted RO-Crates. It integrates with S3-compatible storage (e.g. MinIO) to support RO-Crate storage, versioning, and crate existence checks.

The validator is designed to be deployable as an API using Docker³⁰ and Docker Compose³¹. The reference deployment includes a Flask application, Celery-based³² asynchronous task processing for RO-Crate validation, and webhook support for notifying other downstream tooling and systems of validation results. The provided README and Docker Compose configuration describe a complete setup workflow: cloning the repository, configuring shared environment variables via an .env file, starting the stack with `docker compose up -build`, and configuring a MinIO bucket (including enabling versioning) to store and track RO-Crate objects. For development scenarios, an alternative Docker Compose file is provided to build and test locally modified containers. The internal project structure separates routing, services, tasks, and utilities (e.g. configuration, MinIO interaction, webhooks) to support maintainability and extension. The API includes routes to upload, validate, and retrieve results.

Within the Five Safes TES architecture, the initial operational use case for the validator is at the Submission Layer of TES (this is the main entry point for a researcher submitting work) and at the post-workflow execution / egress stage, rather than running “inside” a TRE during execution (see [Figure 1](#)). In this pattern, RO-Crates would be validated at submission to assess conformance to the Five Safes RO-Crate profile before execution is scheduled, and at egress before leaving the trusted environment. The Validator API

²⁷ <https://github.com/eScienceLab/Cratey-Validator>

²⁸ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/stable/>

²⁹ <https://github.com/crs4/rocrate-validator>

³⁰ <https://www.docker.com>

³¹ <https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

³² <https://docs.celeryq.dev/en/stable/index.html>

described above will be used at these stages to assess that RO-Crates produced by Five Safes TES components meet the Five Safes RO-Crate specification. The service will not perform statistical disclosure control or other checks on the data contained within the crate; this is left to other services within the TRE. As such, passing validation does not mean that an RO-Crate is inherently safe, only that it contains valid metadata in the expected format.

Work is ongoing to refine the deployment model such that a validator instance can operate *within* a federated node. This includes introducing appropriate caching of required information so that a validator instance operating within a node can run self-contained. In parallel, there is ongoing work to identify and define more optimal RO-Crate profiles for use within a federated TRE, and to design validation profiles that support those more optimal profiles.

To support validation of crates following the Five Safes RO-Crate profile, progress has been made on defining formal validation rules using SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language), an RDF validation language³³. This work has been broken into two phases. The first phase has been integrated into rocrate-validator in a GitHub fork³⁴ and includes checks on metadata about people, organizations, projects, and workflow executions. The second phase will add further checks around BagIt packaging and metadata specific to particular phases of the review process (e.g. approval of workflow execution, disclosure control). When complete, the validation rules will be integrated into the RO-Crate Validation Service. This will allow RO-Crates generated within TREs to be fully validated against the profile specification before being released or exchanged, improving standardisation and interoperability across different components.

Development of the formal validation rules has in turn brought attention to areas of the specification which could be updated or clarified, which will feed into the next version of Five Safes RO-Crate.

Other ongoing work includes alignment with the TREvolution³⁵ project (part of the DARE UK programme), which promotes broad use of validatable RO-Crates for provenance in federated scenarios. As part of this work, multiple DARE UK Early Adopter projects³⁶ - pilot projects testing and integrating TREvolution outputs - are being supported in their adoption of Five Safes RO-Crate, predominantly in health-focused TRE contexts. Feedback from those Early Adopter projects will influence the next version of Five Safes RO-Crate; updates are expected to allow a greater range of research processes to be described (not just workflows), and to support compatibility with a greater range of TRE architectures (not just ones which align with this demonstrator). While these projects focus on the UK

³³ SHACL, <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

³⁴ <https://github.com/eScienceLab/rocrate-validator/releases/tag/five-safes-0.7.3-beta>

³⁵ TREvolution, <https://dareuk.org.uk/trevolution/>

³⁶ <https://dareuk.org.uk/how-we-work/ongoing-activities/dare-uk-early-adopters/>

TRE landscape, the outputs should be beneficial to all TRE providers. Building on the feedback gathered from the TRevolution Early Adopters, the updated Five Safes RO-Crate profile will introduce greater flexibility beyond workflow-centric use cases. As this new profile matures, an important next step is to validate it against the ENTRUST driver projects.

4.2. Evolution of TRE-FX into Five Safes TES

There are many dependencies and required interactions of TRE-specific components to both consume and feed Five Safe RO-Crates with the appropriate provenance. For this reason, Demonstrator components have evolved to focus less on RO-Crates as an end-to-end transport format, and instead leverage GA4GH TES to facilitate task execution interoperability, while re-focusing Five Safes RO-Crate usage to output provenance packages (i.e. output control).

4.3. Architecture overview

Fig. 2 - Five Safes TES layered architecture, with relevant components, with a single example TRE.

Figure 2 describes the main components of the Demonstrator. Architecturally, the differences between the first (D19.1) and second (D20.1) deployable demonstrators are minor. The same basic architectural principles apply, in that:

- There is a centralised federation **Submission Service**, presenting a GUI and a REST API.
 - In D20.1 the **Submission Service** is implemented by the Five Safes TES **Submission UI** and **Submission API**.
 - The **Submission Service** interacts with **AAAI components**
 - In D20.1 localised components are substituted for the EOSC-ENTRUST equivalents, but built on the same standards, primarily **OpenID Connect**.
 - An **Artifact Store** is used for transfer between the Submission Service and TREs.
 - The store uses **Amazon S3** as an object store API; specifically D20.1 uses **MinIO** to implement this.
 - The **Submission Service** uses **Submission Orchestration Queues** to make project submissions available to target TREs
- Connections from each TRE are made outbound only, and only one component (the **Job Controller**) makes connections beyond the TRE boundary.
 - In D20.1 the **Job Controller** is implemented by the Five Safes TES **TRE Agent**.
- TREs retain control of Federation and Project participation
 - The **Job Controller** synchronises Project membership with the federation **Submission Service** and can approve or reject Projects, and Users on those Projects at any time.
- The **Job Controller** fetches submissions and revalidates them locally.
 - If referenced projects, users, containers, inputs and described outputs are valid:
 - The **Job Controller** will ingress supporting inputs from the **Artifact Store**
 - The **Job Controller** will add project environment specific details to the submission, such as **data access ephemeral credentials**.
 - The **Job Controller** will hand over the submission to the **TES Backend** for execution.
- The TRE has an **Intermediary Store**, to make project submission inputs and outputs available across the different TRE components.
 - The store uses the **Amazon S3 API specification**; specifically D20.1 uses a localised **MinIO** deployment to implement this.
- The **TES Backend** writes outputs to the **Intermediary Store** and they await approval for release from **Output Control**.
- TREs retain control of egress approval, using a portal for **Output Control** where an **Output Controller** must log in and approve outputs for release back to the **Submission Service**.

- In D20.1 **Output Control** is implemented by the Five Safes TES **Egress** application.
- The **Job Controller** returns approved outputs to the **Submission Service** via the **Artifact Store**.

There are differences in some of the components within that model when compared with the first deployable demonstrator. As stated above, the primary change is the adoption of the GA4GH TES standard as an interface for both submission and execution.

The TRE-FX components used in D19.1 were version v1.186.4³⁷, while the Five Safes TES versions of those components used in D20.1 are a hotfixed release³⁸ derived from v2.14.0³⁹. There has been nearly a year's worth of releases and changes to these components between the two demonstrators from the University of Nottingham and the University of Swansea via the HDR UK and DARE UK programmes.

Furthermore, The Hutch Agent component is no longer used (as described in the [Execution interface](#) changes below).

4.3.1. Submission API TES interface

In D19.1, the Submission API did provide a GA4GH TES interface, but it accepted non-standard payloads that directly referenced Five Safes RO-Crates (profile version 0.4) containing workflow definitions.

The Five Safes TES Submission API, as used in D20.1, now uses a fully standard TES interface, and uses tags, a standard feature of TES, to handle extended “Five Safes TES” metadata. The semantic meaning of these tags is defined by the “Five Safes TES” model, and used as such by the Submission Layer.

The key metadata for federated Five Safes TES submissions is a Project identifier and enumerating the target TREs the submission should be run within. Additional metadata is included in the tags for auditing and provenance purposes.

The Submission API uses this metadata, along with the authentication from the request (via an OIDC Bearer Token, per standard TES) to validate that the requesting user is authorised to make a submission for this Project, to the target TREs specified, and if so, uses the list of target TREs to ensure the submission is queued for those TREs to pick up and execute.

³⁷ <https://github.com/SwanseaUniversityMedical/DARE-Control/releases/tag/v1.186.4-containers>

³⁸ <https://github.com/SwanseaUniversityMedical/DARE-Control/releases/tag/v1.0.0-nottingham-containers>

³⁹ <https://github.com/SwanseaUniversityMedical/DARE-Control/releases/tag/v2.14.0-containers>

4.3.2. Execution TES interface

Formerly (TRE-FX, as used in D19.1), when retrieving queued submissions including a TRE-targeted TES message, the TRE Agent made a new HTTP request to submit a job to the Hutch Agent, on its proprietary API. The Hutch Agent, solely a piece of plumbing middleware, then performed a number of steps (primarily to account for airgapped environments) to prepare execution of the job via WfExS. This approach at the time was fairly brittle, not built on open standards, and not highly compatible with containerised infrastructure approaches. It did however demonstrate the possibility of achieving federated analysis, per D19.1.

Today, in Five Safes TES, the Hutch Agent is no longer required, as standard GA4GH TES is used for execution. The TRE Agent does the minimal necessary TRE-specific preparation of the TES message it receives (primarily injection of environment-specific secrets) and submits that standard TES message to any configured TES backend. D20.1 uses Funnel for this purpose, but any TES implementation can be used. In turn, Funnel could trigger WfExS-managed pipelines (see [WfExS as TES Backend](#)). This approach resolves the issues detailed previously: the brittle plumbing middleware components are not required, open standards are used between components, and – depending on the TES backend selected – all components can fit different infrastructure set-ups, including those based around Docker or Kubernetes.

4.4. WfExS as TES Backend

WfExS cannot directly become a TES backend, as it manages workflows (i.e. sets of tasks), not single task executions. However, to enable the use of WfExS within the Five Safes TES architecture, WfExS can be operationalised behind a TES interface. This involves using Funnel as the TES-facing implementation, while WfExS is invoked internally to orchestrate workflows (see [figure 3](#)).

Fig 3: Integration schema of WfExS as TES Backend in the Five Safes TES architecture of the Demonstrator. The grey arrow corresponds to the missing connection currently being addressed.

This is an ongoing work and tasks carried out include:

- Testing Funnel support for nested container execution models to allow WfExS to operate securely within the containerised TES execution context.

Starting with Funnel v.0.11⁴⁰, backend parameters (i.e. Docker, Singularity/Apptainer) are being exposed when configuring Funnel jobs so that the command line used to create the container instances can be customized. Funnel permits adding custom flags to the command (i.e. flags controlling Docker privileges) or completely replacing Docker instance invocation by other container managers (i.e. Singularity). As such, a nested container execution setup like the one described in the Compute Backend of [figure 3](#) is now possible and has been validated with local tests. BSC Funnel server triggers Singularity-based workflows managed by WfExS, while being WfExS and the selected workflow engine (i.e. Nextflow) themselves Docker containers.

- Verification of workflow staging, localisation, and environment resolution within sealed execution environments under several container-in-container models.

To better understand the technical implications of embedding containers, a study of several container engines has been carried out, comparing Docker, Singularity and Podman and exploring their limitations and capabilities on managing user namespaces, propagating configurations, associated volume mapping restrictions, support to encrypted binds, etc. The best approach was using “Singularity within Singularity” or alternatively, “Singularity within Docker”.

For completing WfExS integration into the Demonstrator, WfExS should map its execution outputs to TES-defined output directories so that they can be returned via the Artifact Store.

4.5. Demonstrator Deployment at BSC and UNOTT

In D19.1’s next steps we declared the intent to “implement the next release in the DARE-UK TRE-FX as the primary testing and validation TRE setup.” This aligns with the desire to track developments in DARE-UK’s efforts as a Work Package goal.

With this in mind, the teams in UNOTT and BSC deployed Five Safes TES across their institutions in order to federate some analyses. This effort informed the development of

⁴⁰ FUNNEL v.0.11: <https://github.com/ohsu-comp-bio/funnel/issues/962>

training materials for doing so (D20.2⁴¹), and ensured that development of necessary features and fixes in the tools was achieved, allowing us to clearly demonstrate that these tools (Five Safes TES) can be deployed and run useful analyses.

4.5.1. Deployed Components

Fig. 4 - Diagram showing organisational sovereignty of federation layer deployments. Note that all connectivity from a TRE is outbound, whether fetching submissions or outputting results.

For the deployment, UNOTT hosted the centralised Submission components, and then each of UNOTT and BSC deployed TRE infrastructure to a similar pattern (see [figure 4](#)), with the necessary components, as follows:

- **Submission Layer (UNOTT)**
 - KeyCloak (with a realm for Submission AAI).
 - used for Researcher identities for making submissions

⁴¹ Couldridge J, Mitchell-White J, D20.2: [Training Package for Digital Objects & Workflows](#)

- also used by both TREs to authenticate and authorise the TRE Agent component
- MinIO for Artifact Storage.
- RabbitMQ as a message broker.
- The Five Safes TES Submission API.
- The Five Safes TES Submission GUI.
- **Controller Layer (UNOTT and BSC)**
 - KeyCloak realms:
 - a realm for TRE Agent AAI to authenticate and authorise TRE Operators.
 - a realm for Egress Portal AAI to authenticate and authorise Output Controllers.
 - MinIO for Intermediary Storage.
 - The Five Safes TES TRE Agent API.
 - with outbound (TRE external) Submission Layer connections to:
 - KeyCloak
 - Artifact Storage
 - Submission API
 - with outbound (TRE internal) connection to the Funnel TES API.
 - The Five Safes TES TRE Agent GUI.
 - The Five Safes TES Egress API.
 - The Five Safes TES Egress GUI.
- **Execution Layer (UNOTT and BSC)**
 - Funnel as a TES Backend
 - with outbound (TRE internal) connection to Intermediate Storage.
 - with inbound (TRE internal) connection from TRE Agent API.
- **Project Data (UNOTT and BSC)**
 - A synthetic OMOP dataset in PostgreSQL was used in each TRE.
 - The datasets were provisioned using the omop-lite⁴² utility.

All components except Funnel were deployed as containers using Docker Compose. Funnel was installed natively on a VM and run as a background service via the Linux systemd System and Service Manager⁴³.

Each Layer was deployed in a VM to the following specification:

- 4 vCPU
- 16GB RAM
- 128GB Disk
- Ubuntu 24.04 LTS

⁴² <https://github.com/health-informatics-uon/omop-lite>

⁴³ <https://systemd.io/>

Once the components were deployed, the federation was configured as follows:

- In the Submission Layer:
 - Users were added for each TRE (to represent the TRE Agent component).
 - Each TRE was registered within the Submission Layer as a federation member TRE, able to be added as a target TRE for Projects
 - A Project was created, and both TREs were added to it.
 - Researcher users were created representing an individual from each organisation.
 - The Researchers were added to the Project.
- In each TRE Agent:
 - TRE Operator and Output Controller users were added to their respective realms.
 - TRE Operators approved the Project and Researchers.

After the configuration was complete, the Submission GUI showed each TRE and Researcher's approved membership of the Project, as well as each TRE's online status (confirmed by a regular heartbeat).

Fig. 5 - Submission Layer Project showing Member TREs' approval status

Fig. 6 - Submission Layer Project showing approved Researcher membership

Fig. 7 - Submission Layer showing registered TREs and their online status

4.5.2. Federated Analysis on the Deployed Demonstrator

To demonstrate some useful analysis, a simple example statistic desired by Driver 3 was selected: the mean value of a measurement (for a given OMOP code) for a given cohort definition within the datasets across the federation.

For demonstration, the code used was “3037532” (chosen due to known appearance in the synthetic datasets, not for clinically sound reasons), and the only cohort inclusion factor was the presence of that measurement.

To calculate a mean using Five Safes TES, the algorithm must be decomposed into a summary statistics stage (which is federated to each dataset node) and an aggregation stage (which occurs where the researcher is, once all summary statistics results have been returned from the federated nodes).

For the demonstration, a python script⁴⁴ was used to submit the summary statistics stage to Five Safes TES and then, when ready, retrieve the results and perform the aggregation stage.

With everything for the federated Project configured, the following process was followed to perform a federated analysis:

- **Researcher**
 - a. A Researcher account for the project signed in to the Submission Layer
 - b. The Researcher retrieved an API access token for their account [Fig. 8]
 - c. The Researcher configured the analysis script [Fig. 9] with:
 - their access token
 - the target Project (ENTRUSTDriver3Demo)
 - the target TREs (BSC and Nottingham 2)
 - d. The Researcher ran the script [Fig. 10], which submitted a TES message to the Submission API to calculate some summary statistics in each TRE.
- **Five Safes TES**
 - a. The Submission API accepted the Researcher’s request submitted by the analysis script
 - b. The Submission API queued the Submission for each TRE
 - c. Each TRE Agent retrieved their queued Submission and validated it
 - d. Each TRE Agent added TRE and Project environment specific data access details, to allow the executed containers to access the Project’s data.
 - e. Each TRE Agent passed the final TES message to Funnel for execution.
 - f. Funnel executed the message, accessing the Project data using the provided secrets.
 - g. Funnel deposited outputs in the Intermediary Store.

⁴⁴Five Safe TES Analytics: <https://github.com/Health-Informatics-UoN/Five-Safes-TES-Analytics>

- h. Each TRE Agent notified their respective TRE's Egress Portal that outputs are ready for checking.
- **Output Controller**
 - a. An Output Controller for each TRE signed in to their TRE's Egress Portal.
 - b. The Output Controller downloaded the outputs to inspect them, then approved them for release. [Fig. 11]
- **Five Safes TES**
 - a. Each Egress Portal informed their TRE Agent of the approval.
 - b. Each TRE Agent released their outputs from the Intermediary Store to the Submission Artifact Store.
 - c. Each TRE Agent notified the Submission API that the Submission was complete.
- **Researcher**
 - a. The Researcher's running script checked the Submission API for completion of the Submission.
 - b. When completed, the script downloaded all outputs for the Submission (one from each TRE).
 - c. With the downloaded summary statistic outputs, the script aggregated them into a final mean value across the datasets, returning that output to the waiting Researcher.

TREs API Access Token

Fig. 8 - Getting a Researcher's API Token from the Submission Layer.

```

GNU nano 8.5                               .env
# TRE-FX Analytics Environment Configuration
# Copy this file to .env and update with your actual values
# ALL VARIABLES BELOW ARE REQUIRED - the application will fail to start without them

# Authentication
TRE_FX_TOKEN=
TRE_FX_PROJECT=ENTRUSTDriver3Demo

# TES (Task Execution Service) Configuration
TES_BASE_URL=http://trefx01-v2.uksouth.cloudapp.azure.com:5034/
TES_DOCKER_IMAGE=harbor.ukserp.ac.uk/dare-trefx/control-tre-sqlpg@sha256:18a8d3b056fd573ec199523fc333c691cd4e7e90ff1c43e59be8314066e1313c

# MinIO Configuration
MINIO_STS_ENDPOINT=http://trefx01-v2.uksouth.cloudapp.azure.com:9000/sts
MINIO_ENDPOINT=trefx01-v2.uksouth.cloudapp.azure.com:9000
MINIO_OUTPUT_BUCKET=entrustdriver3demo5637output

# TRE Configuration
TRE_FX_TRES=Nottingham 2,BSC

```

Fig. 9 - Configuration for the Analysis Script

```

11:50 → python ./analysis_engine.py
Running mean analysis...
Submitting mean analysis to 2 TREs...
Task ID: 426
Task status: 0 - Waiting for Child Submissions To Complete

```

Fig. 10 - Analysis Script running. The summary statistics analysis has been submitted to 2 TREs and the script is waiting for the Submissions to complete, so that it can retrieve and aggregate the results.

The screenshot shows the 'Egress Request: #426 name DEMO: mean analysis test' interface. The request is currently 'Not completed'. Under the 'Minio Bucket' section, the file '427/output.csv' is listed with a download icon and radio buttons for 'Approved', 'Rejected', and 'Undecided' (which is selected). Below this are buttons for 'Complete & Close Request', 'Save', and 'Cancel'. An inset window titled '427_output.csv - KWrite' shows the file's content: 'n,total' on the first line and '4609,229429' on the second line.

Fig. 11 - TRE Egress Portal, and inspecting the downloaded outputs. In the portal the approval status of the outputs can be updated and saved.

The Five Safes TES Submission Layer shows the received TES message for a Submission, and provides up to date status reports of the analysis progress within the target TREs.

DEMO: mean analysis test

Submission ID: 488 Completed

ENTRUSTDriver3Demo Jon Couldridge (Researcher) 11/14/2025 10:58:08

Submission Bucket
Output Bucket

Timeline

- ▶ Started
11/14/2025 10:58:08
- ✔ Completed
11/14/2025 15:21:43
- 🕒 Runtime
4 Hours 23 Minutes and 35 Seconds

Submission Query

```

{
  "id": "488",
  "state": 0,
  "name": "DEMO: mean analysis test",
  "description": "Federated analysis task",
  "inputs": null,
  "outputs": [
    {
      "name": "workdir",
      "description": "analysis test output",
      "url": "s3://entrustdriver3demo5637output",
      "path": "/outputs",
      "type": "DIRECTORY"
    }
  ],
  "resources": null,
  "executors": [
    {
      "image": "harbor.ukserp.ac.uk/dare-trefx/control-tre-sqlpg@sha256:18a8d3b056fd573ec199523fc333c691cd4e7e90ffc43e50be8314066e1313c",
      "command": [
        "--Output=/outputs/output.csv",
        "--Query=WITH user_query AS (\nSELECT value_as_number FROM public.measurement \nWHERE measurement_concept_id = 3637532\nAND value_as_number IS NOT NULL\n)\n\nSELECT\n COUNT(*) AS n,\n SUM(value_as_number) AS total\nFROM user_query;"
      ],
      "workdir": "/app",
      "stdin": null,
      "stdout": null,
      "stderr": null,
      "env": {}
    }
  ],
  "volumes": null,
  "tags": {
    "Project": "ENTRUSTDriver3Demo",
    "tres": "Nottingham 2|BSC"
  },
  "logs": null,
  "creation_time": null
}
                    
```

Fig. 12 - Submission Layer showing the analysis Submission's current status, the Five Safes TES Message that was submitted, and links to the input and output artifact stores for the submission.

	BSC <small>TRE Submission ID: 410</small> ✔ Online	Nottingham 2 <small>TRE Submission ID: 409</small> ✔ Online
Submission Layer Processing	✔ Waiting for Agent To Transfer <small>11 Seconds</small>	✔ Waiting for Agent To Transfer <small>7 Seconds</small>
Tre Layer Processing	✔ Transferred To Pod <small>55 Seconds</small>	✔ Transferred To Pod <small>57 Seconds</small>
Query Processing	✔ Requested Egress <small>4 Hours 22 Minutes and 24 Seconds</small>	✔ Requested Egress <small>2 Minutes and 23 Seconds</small>
Data Egress Processing	✔ Data Out Approved <small>3 Seconds</small>	✔ Data Out Approved <small>2 Seconds</small>
	✔ Completed <small>4 Hours 23 Minutes and 35 Seconds</small> Click to View Output Bucket	✔ Completed <small>3 Minutes and 39 Seconds</small> Click to View Output Bucket

Fig. 13 - Submission Layer showing each TRE's progress status for the submission, including links to the output artifact store now that the submission is complete.

4.6. Analysis Classification and Feasibility

As part of Work Package 20's efforts, we have spent time classifying analyses and assessing feasibility of the different types under certain federation conditions.

This work has been used to comment on the capabilities of Five Safes TES – and therefore this demonstrator, particularly to assess the extent to which the demonstrator might meet Driver use cases – as well as providing a useful illustrative resource⁴⁵ for Researchers and TREs to better understand the impact of different federation approaches and decisions on what analysis is possible given what a TRE finds acceptable. Much of this work is covered in The Work Package 20 Training Package D20.2⁴⁶.

Below we summarise the feasibility of federation for different common statistical tests, as relevant to the Driver use cases we have explored so far, and the capabilities of the second Deployable Demonstrator. This information, along with that expanded upon in D20.2, is valuable for any use case that wants to assess whether they can federate.

4.6.1. Statistics Feasibility

For assessing feasibility of federation, the statistic computed is the relevant information.

Mean ± Standard deviation: These are relatively simple to federate. The mean can be calculated in federation by each TRE calculating the count and the sum of the value (in this example, Age or BMI), then sending these to be aggregated by dividing the grand total value by the grand total count. Similarly, the variance of the overall population can be calculated from the count, the sum, and the sum of squares for a value. This can then be trivially converted into the standard deviation.

Median: Quantiles, including the median, are challenging to calculate in federation, and no set of summary statistics can be used to calculate the median in a single step aggregation like the mean. However, there are approximations of quantiles⁴⁷ that can be calculated in federation, and are usually accurate to within 0.1%. If this is acceptable to the driver, it should be substituted.

Minimum and maximum: These are trivial to federate; each TRE can share its minimum and maximum, and the minimum and maximum of these calculates the overall statistic. However, these statistics can be very disclosive, so their use should be considered carefully.

Counting: Calculating the proportions of people of different sexes in the sample can most simply be calculated by TREs sending over their counts of male and female within the

⁴⁵ <https://health-informatics-uon.github.io/analysis-types-for-TREs/>

⁴⁶ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1m4T3r_eSVowPFEQkQj_C9s2ivLzQMqCqX/

⁴⁷ Computing extremely accurate quantiles Using t-digests <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.04023>

population, then calculating what proportion of the total population these are. The same is true, with more groups to count, for comorbidity.

Chi-square test: The chi-square test is performed on a contingency table. In federation, this table can be prepared from local counts as described above, then the chi-square test performed.

t-test: A one-sample t-statistic can be calculated using the population mean, the sample standard deviation and the sample size. All of these can be federated as above. Two sample t-statistics can be calculated using the same information for different samples.

Kaplan-Meier estimator: Survival analysis is difficult to federate. There is no summary statistic TREs could send to an aggregator to calculate the Kaplan-Meier estimator, so it will not be possible with Five Safes TES.

Multivariate comparison: There are many methods for multivariate comparison. Some, like cluster analysis, will not be possible within Five Safes TES. An example of a multivariate comparison that is possible is Hotelling's T^2 test. This is a multivariate extension of Student's t-test for univariate statistics and requires similar data, the main difference in requirements being that covariances, rather than variance, are required. This is harder to compute and aggregate, but is still possible to federate in Five Safes TES.

4.7. Demonstrated Use Cases

4.7.1. Driver 3: Clinical trial & healthcare data

ENTRUST Driver 3 seeks to approximate the results of a randomised controlled trial (RCT) into adverse events following COVID-19 vaccination, using the Tayside population with data held in the Health Informatics Centre (HIC) TRE. An RCT has inclusion criteria to select who gets to take part in the trial. This will be approximated in the Tayside population by filtering people by similar criteria. The aim is then to carry out the same analysis in federation as in the RCT.

The analysis starts by deriving "Baseline characteristics" to the other basic statistics proposed in the prototype, including subgroup analysis based on vaccination history, and comorbidity.

Baseline characteristics:

- Age
 - Mean \pm Standard deviation
 - Median
 - Minimum
 - Maximum

- Sex
 - percentage in cohort
- BMI
 - Mean \pm Standard deviation
 - Median
 - Minimum
 - Maximum

Though the characteristics are calculated on different variables, we can refer back to the earlier described [analysis classification](#) work, as performed against the relevant statistics:

- **Mean \pm Standard deviation**
- **Median** - complicated to federate unless using suitable approximation methods
- **Minimum and maximum**
- **Counting**

These baseline characteristics will be followed by statistical tests for comparisons of comorbidity.

- **Chi-square test**
- **t-test**
- **Kaplan-Meier estimator** - Not possible with Five Safes TES.
- **Multivariate comparison** - The method for this is currently left unspecified in the prototype, As noted above, some methods will be possible using Five Safes TES, and others will not.

4.7.2. Driver 1: Federated Genomics Workflow Processing

The overall objective of Driver 1 is to enable end-to-end secure, federated workflow execution across multiple TREs for genomic data analysis compliant with Five Safes principles. The Demonstrator is focused exclusively on the distribution and processing of analysis workflows across TREs and does not cover several steps that, in a real genomics use case, would need to be performed before and after the analysis itself. Particularly, the presented use case aims to execute a common Variant Calling pipeline to identify biomarkers related to Colorectal Cancer. The pipeline is nf-core/SAREK⁴⁸, a containerized Nextflow⁴⁹ workflow based on GATK⁵⁰. The sample sequencing data in use corresponds to synthetic colorectal cancer genomic data⁵¹ produced by BSC in the context of the

⁴⁸ nf-core/SAREK: <https://nf-co.re/sarek/3.5.1/>

⁴⁹ Nextflow: <https://www.nextflow.io/>

⁵⁰ GATK: <https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/>

⁵¹ Longitudinal Synthetic Colorectal Cancer Genomic dataset:
<https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD50000000276>

EOSC4Cancer⁵² project. Eventually, the genomic variants detected in each TRE should be aggregated and returned to the researcher, passing through the proper egress processes.

Unlike the Driver 3 prototype, Driver 1 prototype is not yet integrated with the Demonstrator, mainly because the current WfExS integration efforts under TES schema are still ongoing (see [WfExS as TES Backend](#)). For this reason, efforts were focused on conducting a set of tests at the BSC HPC system. Datasets were obtained from the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA)⁵³ and prepared to be used within the Variant Calling pipeline. Test executions demonstrated that pipeline execution ran successfully in the SLURM-based queueing system, but did highlight some data management issues to be considered when automatizing the system.

4.8. Handling data security with workflow orchestrator

TREs have “operational secrets” or data to be protected, such as database connection strings, data locations or other TRE-specific security materials that must be passed into an RO-Crate workflow or/and supplied to WfExS. The sensitive information needed for analysis should be handled in a controlled, auditable, and non-persistent manner. Over the past year, substantial progress has been made across both the Five Safes TES security model and the WfExS workflow execution backend.

4.8.1. TRE Security Information Handling via Five Safes TES

Significant development work has been completed on a rule-based mechanism for providing TRE-specific security information to workflows executed through Five Safes TES. Feature development is complete, and integration testing is currently underway, though full integration into the Demonstrator instance is still in progress.

A TRE can define policy-driven rules specifying the security information required for a given analysis, based on combinations of attributes like project identifiers, user identifiers, sensitivity classifications, or other local constraints. When a TES task is submitted, these rules are evaluated by the TES Agent component, which:

- generates ephemeral credentials scoped to the specific execution request;
- injects the credentials as environment variables into the TES task payload before dispatching it to the TES backend (e.g., Funnel, with the special set of cases of WfExS within Funnel);
- expires the credentials automatically once the execution step no longer requires them;

⁵² EOSC4Cancer: <https://eosc4cancer.eu/>

⁵³ European Genome-Phenome Archive: <https://ega-archive.org/>

- provides default environment variable conventions, ensuring that analysis tools can depend on predictable credential names; and
- supports TRE-specific customisation, allowing more complex mappings or overrides for legacy tools.

This approach fully aligns with the credential-handling model promoted by the HDR UK Federated Analytics Programme and DARE UK TREvolution, ensuring compatibility with UK TRE standardisation efforts.

4.8.2. Enhanced Secrets and Data Handling in WfExS

Parallel work has focused on improving secrets handling, secure staging, and controlled export within WfExS. Current enhancements include:

- Credentials required for data staging or exporting results are provided in a separate, non-persistent credential file, passed only to the relevant data fetcher modules.
- All secure working directories are created as encrypted FUSE-based volumes, with encryption keys generated via Crypt4GH (either installation defaults or user-provided keys).
- Each run-specific working directory receives its own symmetric key, encrypted using either the user-provided keys or the default ones.
- Data confidentiality is enforced using dataset propagation flags (disclosable, cacheable, clonable), preventing copies, accidental export or reuse of sensitive intermediate data.
- All sensitive information (labelled as “undisclosable”) is scrubbed from exported WRROCs, provenance objects, workflow definitions, and execution logs.

Together, these improvements provide a robust security foundation for federated workflow execution within TREs and ensure that both credentials and sensitive inputs are managed in line with Five Safes principles.

5. Results

The Year 2 Demonstrator has successfully validated the feasibility of executing federated, governance-aware workflows across two independent TREs, demonstrating real progress beyond the initial proof-of-concept delivered in Year 1. The Demonstrator was able to (i) validate its portability and architectural consistency and (ii) execute tasks in both TREs

using a unified submission flow, with each site enforcing its local governance mechanisms (i.e. authentication, project configuration, output controls) before contributing results to the federation. Moreover, the setup permits high flexibility to TREs when providing their own compute backend. Using Funnel, simple federated analyses were executed across both TREs, illustrating a low-overhead route for Driver 3–type use cases in which each TRE processes local data and returns a partial result for secure aggregation outside the TREs. These federated computations were executed successfully end-to-end, proving that the Demonstrator now supports real, cross-site computation. In addition, the Demonstrator architecture proved reproducible across sites, with BSC and UNOTT deploying equivalent configurations and demonstrating consistent behaviour. In parallel, additional components and services were created or further developed with the ultimate purpose of being integrated in a future iteration of the Demonstrator.

On one side, WfExS was used to execute complex genomic workflows for Driver 1 within the BSC TRE, demonstrating the system’s ability to support multi-step, provenance-rich computations in environments with strict confidentiality requirements. Although WfExS is not a TES backend, recent developments in Funnel allow nested container execution, creating a practical route for Funnel-triggered WfExS runs as Singularity-in-Singularity or Singularity-in-Docker processes. The integration tests confirmed that WfExS can operate within a TES-driven execution context, moving towards a TES-native support in future Demonstrator iterations.

On the other side, the RO-Crate Validation Service has reached a mature and deployable state. Its integration with asynchronous task handling and object storage enables TREs to treat validation as a modular and independent service, set either as an internal or external TRE service. Validation tests confirmed that the application correctly identified missing metadata, incomplete provenance, and structural inconsistencies in test RO-Crates, demonstrating its utility in enforcing Five Safes RO-Crate profile requirements. The service is expected to play a key role in future egress governance and provenance verification workflows.

Overall, the Year 2 results establish that the Demonstrator is capable of delivering a minimal but functional federated workflow execution environment aligned with the goals of EOSC-ENTRUST.

6. Discussion

The Year 2 Demonstrator shows that the ENTRUST reference implementation of the workflow execution architecture is moving from a proof-of-concept into a practical deployment for real federated analytics, proving its technical feasibility. Deployments at BSC and UNOTT confirmed that two independent TREs can run a shared,

governance-aware workflow execution flow while retaining full control over their internal policies, authentication, secrets handling, and compute setup.

A central evolution this year has been the shift from the end-to-end use of Five Safes RO-Crates envisioned in D19.1 toward a more practical architecture centred on the Five Safes TES Weave. While Workflow and Workflow Run RO-Crates remain essential for structured provenance and, potentially, egress metadata phase, using them as a full transport mechanism for governance metadata proved too expensive in terms of integration - at least at the current development stage. Five Safes TES, by contrast, offers a less structured framework focused solely on achieving distributed computation interoperability while preserving Five Safes principles. This shift has simplified the implementation, reduced integration overhead, minimized the adoption barrier, and provided a more realistic path to interoperability with external initiatives.

The use of an RO-Crate Validation Service further strengthens this architecture shift. While not yet embedded end-to-end in the Demonstrator, the service is expected to play a key role in submission checks, output verification, and potentially, automated egress approval. Moreover, its planned ability to run either inside a TRE or as a trusted external verifier will create flexibility for different governance models.

A technically important aspect explored this year is the use of nested container execution models within TREs. Many TREs restrict direct use of Docker due to security concerns, relying instead on container engines such as Singularity/Apptainer that avoid privileged operations. However, executing workflow engines like WfExS inside a TES-managed container often requires container-in-container strategies such as Singularity-in-Singularity or Singularity-in-Docker. This approach has clear advantages: it isolates workflow execution environments, ensures reproducibility across sites, and avoids loosening TRE security constraints. At the same time, it introduces challenges that TREs must evaluate carefully, including performance overhead, the need to correctly propagate user and group identifiers, limitations in nested mount propagation, and the risk of obscuring provenance if container layers become too deeply nested. Best practice emerging from this work suggests that TREs should adopt minimal, controlled container bases for nested execution, ensure proper cgroup isolation, and maintain explicit provenance capture at the outermost execution level to avoid losing traceability inside nested layers. These considerations will be important to address as execution scenarios scale to more complex workflows.

Overall, the Year 2 results confirm that federated workflow execution is technically viable across TREs using the Five Safes TES architecture while highlighting important areas where standardisation and refinement are still required. For example, better integrating provenance profiles and RO-Crate practices across TREs; defining standard approaches for secrets propagation; and ensuring that nested containerisation remains reliable and compliant across a wider range of infrastructures. The progress achieved this year

provides a strong basis for addressing these challenges, becoming ready for deeper integration of governance, accountability, and provenance capabilities in Year 3.

7. Next steps

- Complete integration of WfExS into the Demonstrator as an eligible TES compute backend. It would imply:
 - Properly configure Funnel to support in a secure manner nested container executions of workflows in TREs (e.g., Singularity-in-Singularity / Singularity-in-Docker)
 - Integrate WfExS with Demonstrator Artifacts Storage (S3) and Egress module
- Explore the most suitable integration of the RO-Crate Validation Service into the Demonstrator workflow, enabling automated validation at submission and egress, and supporting WP18 accountability and audit mechanisms. It would imply:
 - Develop a deployment approach that allows a validator instance to operate within a federated node.
 - Introduce caching approach to enable the validator to run in federated node without external network access
 - Identify and define improved RO-Crate profiles (e.g. updated Five Safes, TREcrate) for federated TREs.
 - Update the Five Safes RO-Crate specification where ambiguities or gaps are identified
 - Extend the profile to describe a wider range of research processes beyond linear workflows.
 - Design corresponding (SHACL) validation profiles to support these profiles.
 - Finalise formal SHACL validation rules for updated Five Safes RO-Crate profile.
- Integrate the enhanced secrets-handling mechanisms already developed under WP 20 Task 2 into Five Safes TES components,
- Further strengthen alignment with ENTRUST Drivers (Driver 1 and Driver 3) by supporting their analyses and workflow processes, increasing stability, and extending coverage to Driver requirements
 - Finalise use case (so far lots of information gathered but formal use case document not produced)
 - Demonstrate as many analyses as possible on Five Safes TES
 - Simple stats should mostly be demonstrable in 2-stage today (starting with mean), so go on to demonstrate all captured in the use case that are possible

- Multivariate comparison may be demonstrable as 2-stage, depending on the chosen methods for calculation; formal capture of the use case will include relevant details and allow accurate comment on feasibility.
- Enhance reproducibility and provenance tracking, ensuring full capture of nested container context, TES task lineage, and workflow-level metadata to support traceability and automated disclosure control.
- Prepare for integration with WP18's Accountability Framework, including testing of event-capture mechanisms as designed in the AAAI design document, mapping workflow events to accountability requirements, and exploring automated compliance reporting.
- Explore semi-automatic or automatic approaches for disclosing intermediary results of federated analysis within the network aligned with Demonstrator's architecture.

8. Impact

The Year 2 demonstrator advances ENTRUST by delivering a deployable, federated execution environment that complies with the Five Safes model. It supports secure, provenance-rich workflows across TRE boundaries and aligns with broader European and UK TRE ecosystems. Through alignment with HDR UK and TRevolution, the demonstrator leverages a maturing interoperability framework with real-world adoption. Internally, it enables ENTRUST Drivers to execute realistic workflows, providing evidence of cross-site federation and secure execution.

Ultimately, this work positions WP20 as a foundation for future EOSC-level federated analytics and reinforces ENTRUST's mission to build trusted, secure, interoperable analytics infrastructures for sensitive data across Europe.